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Review Article

Exploring The Overview on Investigation of Isatin Hybrids as Potential Cancer Cell Degradar

Hafsa*, Lirin Mary M K, Aghil Krishna T, Aparna S

St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy, Cherthala, Alappuzha, 688524

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ABSTRACT

Isatin (1H indole 2,3-dione), one of the heterocyclic scaffold, identified in humans and various plant species. Isatin and its derivatives are synthesized synthetically by many researchers due to its diverse pharmacological actions like anticancer, anti-TB, antimicrobial, antifungal, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-HIV etc. Based on the literature surveys, confirms the profile of isatin derivatives and their pharmacological importance. This review represents the development of novel isatin analogues as a potent chemotherapeutic agent. Structural modification of isatin by substitution at position N, carbonyl groups at position 2 and 3 leads to the development of biologically potential analogues. It also include the evidence of various literature surveys. Discovery of new isatin hybrid molecule via hybridization is one of the approach to overcome drug resistance, improve efficiency, reduce toxicity and enhance specificity. Structural activity relationship also represents provide the development of novel isatin analogues having potent activity and less toxicity. This can be utilised for future development of novel derivatives.

INTRODUCTION

Isatin is one of the important heterocyclic compound utilized in organic synthesis and biological application. Isatin is having molecular formula $C_6H_5NO_2$ and chemically 1H indole 2,3-dione / indole quinone used to synthesize wide range of heterocyclic scaffold for various drug synthesis[1]. More advances during last 25 years

based on the use of isatins on organic synthesis and various biological applications. In 1841, Erdmann and Laurent synthesized isatin by oxidation reaction of indigo in presence of nitric acid and chromic acid[2].

Isatin, also found from several plants, animals and fungi. It is an important component of coal tar. It can be synthesized by Sand Meyer reaction i.e.,

*Corresponding Author: Hafsa

Address: St. Joseph's College of Pharmacy, Cherthala, Alappuzha, 688524

Email ✉: hafsanaseem937@gmail.com

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cyclization of the product obtained by the condensation of chloral hydrate, aniline and hydroxylamine in sulfuric acid[3].

It exists in two forms, lactum and lactim form[4].

Furthermore, substituted isatin compounds are also naturally exists. Eg, methoxy phenyl pentyl isatin, extracted from tumerigenic plant *Melochia tomentosa* in the caribbean. Isatins are also discovered in fungi, *Streptomyces albus* and *Chaetomium globosum*[5].

Isatin scaffold possess various pharmacological properties including analgesic[6], anti-cancer[7], anti-inflammatory[8], anti-tubercular[9], anti-microbial[10], anti-fungal[11] and anti-viral[12].

Structure of isatin based drugs [13-15]:

Sunitinib

Semaxinib

Toceranib

Nintedanib

Oranitinib

Biologically active analogues are prepared by incorporating pharmacophore into the heterocycles.

Discovery of various biologically active agents by substitution of isatins at N or Phenyl ring replacing C2 and C3 Oxygen, especially for anti-tumor agents[16]. Isatin is formed as Tryptophan or Epinephrine (Adrenaline) metabolites in humans. Endogenous isatin block *Monoamine oxidase* (MAO) by binding to MAO-B isoform. Isatin can be directly synthesized chemically, so medicinal chemists are more encouraged to synthesize various isatin derivatives in search for various pharmacological actions. Various isatin hybrids also acts as Tyrosine kinase receptor inhibitors

(iRTK). These inhibitory effect produced is due to its indolic behaviour which is similar to natural substrate of kinases i.e., ATP. Various studies shows the evidence of anti-cancerous activity of isatin derivatives by interact with other kinases.

Thus isatin derivatives displays anti-cancer, anti-tubercular, anti-malarial, anti-fungal, antibacterial, anticonvulsant, anti-leishmanial and anti-viral activities. For the discovery of drugs in cancer therapy, researchers conducted more studies on isatin derivatives. Sunitinib and Toceranib are approved medications for various cancer types. Semaxanib, Orantinib and Nintedanib are the pursuing clinical trial medications [17].

Cancer is becoming a serious threat across the world. According to WHO Global Health Observatory Report from 2018, 9.6 million people died due to cancer. Although the recent advancement in cancer therapy continues, novel drugs with higher potency, selectivity and decreased toxicity are still needed. Indeed, the successful cancer treatment will arise from understanding the basics of cell cycle [18].

Eukaryotic cell growth and division are occurred at three phases: late G1, G2/M and Metaphase to Anaphase transition. These are the 'checkpoints'

that ensures the order, integrity and fidelity of the key cell cycle events.

Development of novel synthetic compounds with more therapeutic benefit is the major challenges for the researchers. For the treatment of complex disease like cancer, Molecular design based on the multitarget ligand paradigm, combines active heterocyclic pharmacophores into single molecule. The resulting hybrids shows variety of mechanisms and acts as promising lead for therapies [19].

CHEMISTRY

Isatin, a heterocyclic scaffold, also known as 1H-indole-2,3-dione and indole quinone having Nitrogen atom at position 1 and two Carbonyl group at position 2 and 3. It comprise of six and five membered ring as cyclic planars [20].

Possible isatin hybrids substitutions

VARIOUS SUBSTITUTED ISATIN HYBRIDS [21-22]

Isatin-1,2,3-Triazole Hybrids

Isatin-Thiazole Hybrids

Isatin Thiazolidinedione Hybrids

Isatin Benzimidazole Hybrids

Isatin-Imidazole Hybrids

Isatin-Benzofuran Hybrids

Isatin-Coumarin Hybrids

Isatin-Imine Hybrids

Isatin-Quinoline Hybrids

Isatin-Chalcone Hybrids

Isatin Sulfonamide Hybrids

Isatin-Quinazoline Hybrids

Isatin-Pyridine Hybrids

Isatin possess many pharmacological properties like anti-cancer, anti-fungal, anti-viral, anti-malarial, anti-TB etc. Among these actions its cytotoxic potential and its potentiality on different cancer cells are previously studied by many researchers shown in figure 1[23]. Isatin produces tumor inhibitory action via different mechanisms consist of apoptosis induction, cell cycle arrest, anti-angiogenesis, topoisomerases inhibition, epigenetic regulation, inhibition of P13K/AKT/mTOR pathway. Isatin derivatives also acts as *histone deacetylases* (HDAC) inhibitor, carbonic anhydrase inhibitor, epidermal growth factor receptor-*tyrosin kinase*(EGFR-TK) inhibitor, tubulin inhibitor and thereby inhibit further proliferation of tumor cells shown in figure[24].

Figure 1- Cytotoxic potentiality of Isatin

Figure 2 – Mechanism of inhibition of isatin.

SYNTHESIS SCHEME FOR ISATIN AS ANTI-NEOPLASTIC AGENT

Sandmeyer synthesis is one of the popular method of synthesizing isatin and its derivatives. But it is

limited to analogues of basic nature. There are various alternative techniques for synthesizing distinct isatin congeners as shown below [25-30].

N-substituted isatin derivatives

C2-Substituted isatin Derivatives

C3-Substituted Isatin Derivatives

C5-Substituted isatin Derivatives

Spiro Derivatives

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Yani Hou *etal***, reviewed that Derivatives **a** and **b** showed potent anti-tumor activity and active against multi-drug resistant cancer cells. Derivative **c** showed broad spectrum anti-cancer activity and Derivative **d** having IC50 value at Nano molar level was highly active against different cancer cells [31-33].

similar activity against apoptosis sensitive and resistant cells [35-36].

2. **K. L. Vineet *et al.***, reviewed on synthesis of isatin derivatives as cytotoxic and anti-proliferative agents and these derivatives were synthesized using substitution at position N, C2 and C3. Also reviewed on synthesizing derivatives using mono, di or tri substitution of the aryl ring [34].

3. **Nikolai M. Evdokimov *et al.*** Reviewed on evaluation of indirubin derivatives and related isatin heterocycles against cancer cells with apoptosis sensitive as well as apoptosis resistant cells. Most of the compounds shows

4. **Sulayman A. Ibrahim *et al.***, synthesize various isatin derivatives and those compounds were tested against K562, HepG2 and HT-29 cell lines. All the synthesized compounds showed anticancer action, where compound **4e** was found most powerful with IC₅₀ value 24.9μM, 20.27μM and 6.10μM respectively [37].

5. **Ibrahim *et al*** in 2016 developed a series of bis isatin-hydrazide derivatives and evaluate their anti-cancer potential against HepG2 (liver), MCF-7 (breast) and HCT-116 (colon) cell lines. Most of the compounds showed moderate action, while compound **5a** exhibit potent cytotoxicity against MCF-7 and HCT-16 with IC₅₀ value 1.8 μ M and 3.31 μ M with respect to standard doxorubicin. Compound **5a** also found active against HepG2 with IC₅₀ 6.99 μ M [38].

6. **Yu-Ou Teng *et al*** synthesized 43 novel di/tri substituted isatin derivatives against human T lymphocyte cells Jurkat using MTT assay via camptothecin as positive control. Compound **6d** showed potent anti-proliferative action with IC₅₀ 0.03 μ M than other derivatives. Further studies proved that it exhibit action through mitochondrial apoptotic pathway by apoptosis induction [39-41].

7. **Abdel-Aziz *et al*** synthesized isatin-benzoazine scaffolds and are screened for anti-cancer action towards HT-29(colon), ZR-75(breast) and A-549(lung) cancer cell lines. Compounds **7b-d**, isatin-phthalazine derivatives exhibit potent anti-cancer action, compound **7c** with IC₅₀ value 9.5 μ M showed more potent action against NCI-H6AR cancer cell lines [42].

8. In 2020, **Al-Wabli *et al***, evaluated the antiproliferative activity of novel isatin-based conjugates on HT-29, ZR-75, and A-549 cell lines. Compound **8m** had strong antiproliferative properties in vitro compared to other conjugates. All evaluated human cancer cell lines had an average IC₅₀ value of 1.17 M, nearly seven times higher than the standard sunitinib (IC₅₀ 8.11 M) [43].

9. In 2020, **Nazari *et al*** synthesized triazol/spiroindolinequinazoline dione, triazol/indolin-3-thiosemicarbazone, and triazol/thiazolindolin-2-one conjugates for

anticancer properties. The provided compounds were tested for their cytotoxic ability against various cancer lines, including A375, PC3, LNCaP, MDA, MB231, and normal cell HDF. The majority of chemicals were discovered to be more potent than the positive control. The triazol-linked oxindol-thiosemicarbazone analogue **9b** demonstrated remarkable potency against all investigated cancer cell lines, with IC₅₀ values ranging from 15.32 to 29.23 M compared to the reference etoposide [44-45].

10. **Kumar et al** in 2020 demonstrated a one-pot multicomponent synthesis of isatin-derived imidazole hybrids with dual-purpose anti-inflammatory and cancer properties. Anticancer activity was tested on MCF-7 (breast cancer cell line) and MCF-10A (normal breast epithelial cells) using MTT assay. Compared to the manufactured hybrids, compound **10m** resulted in 40% cell death in MCF-7 cells at 0.75 M and 70% survival in MCF 10A cells at 8.0M. Compound **10m** demonstrated a 10-fold increase in cytotoxicity against the breast cancer cell line [46].

SAR of isatin as anti-cancer agent

Structure activity relationship, relates isatin scaffold with its pharmacological action, which is important for designing novel isatin derivatives with improved potency, reduced toxicity and better bioavailability [47]. From the literature surveys, reported that various substitution possess diverse pharmacological actions. Carbonyl group in isatin linked with hydrazine, imines or hydrazides possess potent inhibition of CDK and kinase [48].

Imidazole and pyrrole linked derivatives acts as potent receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) inhibition. Substitution at aromatic or aliphatic moiety leads to destabilization of microtubules [49]. Para or Meta substitution produce potent anti-cancer action as compared to Ortho substituted derivatives. Halogenated derivatives acts as potent antitumor agent [50-51].

CONCLUSION

Isatin is used extensively for synthesizing diverse molecules. Isatin molecules can be exists naturally as well as synthetically. It can be synthesized by various methods by condensation of aromatic/aliphatic substituted amines. Various isatin analogues possess diverse pharmacological

actions like anticancer, antimicrobial, antiviral, anti TB, antimalarial etc.

This review aims to reveal the rationalized information regarding isatin analogues on their anti-cancer efficiency. Based on the information from previously cited literatures, anti-proliferative action of isatin was evaluated for renal, breast, lungs, leukaemia, colon, liver, melanoma, kidney, sarcoma and pancreatic cancer. Isatin analogues exerts their anti- proliferative action by binding on targets CDK2, EGFR, VEGFR-2, Bax, Bcl2 etc. Various structural derivatization like halogenation on aromatic ring, substitution at carbonyl group at C3 position, substitution at C2 and N- substitution will improve anticancer potential.

By designing and developing isatin hybrids with various heterocycles to develop novel therapeutic approach with more economic, safer and efficient derivatives. Isatin, one of the versatile heterocycle acts as promising lead for future to develop potential anticancer agents.

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